

Solving neural differential equation by using neural network

by
Muhammad Junaid Aslam
CIIT/FA21-RMT-54/ISB
MS Thesis
In
Mathematics

COMSATS University Islamabad, Islamabad Campus
Pakistan

Fall, 2021

Contents

1	Introduction	4
1.1	Overview	4
1.2	Neural Network Method	5
1.3	Solving differential equations by Neural Networks	5
1.4	Advantages of Neural Network Method for Solving Differential Equation	6
1.5	Historical background of Neural Differential Equation	6
1.6	Uses of deep Neural Differential Equations	7
1.6.1	Solving Differential Equations	7
1.6.2	Approximating Function	8
1.6.3	Data Compression	8
1.6.4	Optimal Control	8
1.6.5	Stochastic Processes	8
2	Preliminaries of Neural Networks	9
2.1	What is Neural Network?	9
2.2	Biological Neural Network	9
2.3	Mathematical model of Artificial Neural Network	11
2.4	Activation Function	12
2.4.1	Sigmoid Function	12
2.4.2	Linear Activation Function	13
2.5	Neural Network Architecture	14
2.5.1	Feed Forward Neural Networks	14
2.5.2	Radial Basis Function(RBF) Neural Networks	14
2.5.3	Hopfield Networks	15
3	Formulation and Implementation of ANN Methods for Solving Differential Equations	15
3.1	Neural Network as Universal Approximation	15
3.2	Universal Approximation Theorem	16

List of Figures

1	Neural Network	9
2	Biological Neural Network	10

3	Mathematical model of ANN	12
4	sigmoid activation function	13

List of Tables

1 Introduction

Artificial neural networks, or neural networks, represent a technology that is rooted in many disciplines like mathematics, physics, statistics, computer science and engineering. Neural networks have various applications in the area of mathematical modelling, pattern recognition, signal processing and time-series analysis, etc. It is an emerging field for researchers and scientists in the industry and academics to work on.

1.1 Overview

A neural network is a series of algorithms that endeavors to recognize underlying relationships in a set of data through a process that mimics the way the human brain operates. In this sense, neural networks refer to systems of neurons, either organic or artificial in nature. An ANN consists of a large number of interconnected processing nodes, called neurons, that work together to learn patterns in data. Each neuron in an ANN receives input from one or more other neurons, and applies a mathematical function to that input to produce an output signal. The output signals from each neuron are then fed as input to other neurons in the network, creating a complex web of interconnected processing units. As we know Neural networks have various applications in the area of mathematical modelling, pattern recognition, signal processing and time-series analysis, etc. Also, many problems in science and engineering can be modelled with the use of differential equations such as problems in physics, chemistry, biology and mathematics. Due to the importance of differential equations, many methods have been developed for solving them, but they have their own shortcomings. The objective of this thesis is to provide the readers with a sound understanding of the foundations of neural network, comprehensive introduction to neural network methods for solving differential equations along with the recent developments in the techniques. The main purpose to write this textbook is stated in its title An Introduction to Neural Network Methods for Differential Equations. This book aims to get started with the neural network techniques for solving differential equations easily, quickly and pleasantly to beginners, regardless of their background—physics, chemistry, mathematics or engineering. This book is a comprehensive text on neural network methods for solving differential equations, and the subject matter is presented in an organized and systematic way.

1.2 Neural Network Method

Neural network methods can solve both ordinary and partial differential equations that relies on the function approximation capabilities of feed forward neural networks and results in a solution written in a closed analytic form. This form employs a feed forward neural network as a basic approximation element whose parameters are adjusted to minimize an appropriate error function. Training of the neural network can be done by any optimization technique which in turn requires the computation of the gradient of the error with respect to the network parameters. In this method, a trial solution of the differential equation is written as a sum of two parts. The first part satisfies the initial or boundary conditions and contains no adjustable parameters. Second part is constructed so as to not affect the initial or boundary conditions and involves a feed forward neural network by containing adjustable parameters. Hence by construction the trial solution, the initial or boundary conditions are satisfied and the network is trained to satisfy the differential equation.

1.3 Solving differential equations by Neural Networks

Solving differential equations is a fundamental task in many areas of science and engineering. In recent years, there has been growing interest in using artificial neural networks (ANNs) to solve differential equations. More specifically, the idea is to use ANNs to approximate the solution of a differential equation, rather than using traditional numerical methods. One approach to using ANNs for solving differential equations is to use them to directly learn the solution of the differential equation. This involves training the ANN on a data set of input-output pairs, where the inputs are the values of the independent variable and the outputs are the corresponding values of the dependent variable. The ANN is then able to estimate the value of the dependent variable at any point in the domain of the differential equation. Another approach is to use ANNs to approximate the differential equation itself. This involves training the ANN to learn the relationship between the derivatives of the dependent variable and the values of the dependent variable and independent variable. Once this relationship is learned, the ANN can be used to estimate the derivatives of the dependent variable at any point in the domain of the differential equation. There are several advantages to using ANNs for solving differential equations, including their ability to handle complex and nonlin-

ear systems, their ability to learn from data, and their ability to generalize to unseen data. However, there are also some challenges, such as the need for large data sets and the potential for over fitting. Overall, the use of ANNs for solving differential equations is an active area of research, and there is much ongoing work to improve the accuracy and efficiency of these methods. differential equation problems arising in many sciences and engineering applications.

1.4 Advantages of Neural Network Method for Solving Differential Equation

A neural network based model for the solution of differential equations provides the following advantages over the standard numerical methods: (a) The neural network based solution of a differential equation is differentiable and is in closed analytic form that can be used in any subsequent calculation. On the other hand most other techniques offer a discrete solution or a solution of limited differentiability. (b) The neural network based method to solve a differential equation provides a solution with very good generalization properties. (c) Computational complexity does not increase quickly in the neural network method when the number of sampling points is increased while in the other standard numerical methods computational complexity increases rapidly as we increase the number of sampling points in the interval. (d) The method is general and can be applied to the systems defined on either orthogonal box boundaries or on irregular arbitrary shaped boundaries (e) Model based on neural network offers an opportunity to tackle in real (f) The method can be implemented on parallel architectures.

1.5 Historical background of Neural Differential Equation

Deep neural networks for solving ordinary and partial differential equations have gained significant attention in recent years due to their potential to address a wide range of problems in various fields such as physics, engineering, finance, and computer vision. The roots of neural networks for differential equations can be traced back to the 1990s when neural networks were first used for solving differential equations. In 1993, Steven Smale introduced the concept of using a neural network to approximate a dynamical system. In

1994, K. Hornik and A. Stinchcombe proposed the multilayer feedforward neural network as a universal approximator for continuous functions, including differential equations. However, due to the limited computational power of the time, these early attempts were largely experimental and limited in scope. The field of deep learning experienced a resurgence in the 2010s, thanks to advances in computing power and the availability of large data sets. In 2014, Siraj Raval proposed using neural networks to solve differential equations. In the same year, Alex Graves introduced the Neural Turing Machine (NTM), a neural network architecture capable of learning algorithms by training on examples of input-output pairs. In 2017, the concept of using neural networks for solving differential equations gained significant momentum when the deep learning community proposed the concept of Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs). PINNs are a neural network-based approach to solving partial differential equations by incorporating physical principles as constraints on the network's output. This approach has been applied to various problems in fluid dynamics, heat transfer, and mechanics. Since then, numerous researchers have proposed different neural network architectures and algorithms for solving differential equations, including Variational Autoencoder Networks (VAENs), Residual Neural Networks (ResNets), and Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs). The field of deep learning for differential equations is still evolving, and researchers continue to explore new techniques and architectures to improve the accuracy and efficiency of these methods.

1.6 Uses of deep Neural Differential Equations

Deep neural differential equations (DNDEs) are a recent development in the field of machine learning that combine deep neural networks with differential equations. DNDEs have shown great promise in various applications in mathematics. Here are some uses of DNDEs in the mathematics field:

1.6.1 Solving Differential Equations

DNDEs can be used to solve complex differential equations numerically. This involves learning the solution to a differential equation by minimizing the difference between the predicted solution and the actual solution. DNDEs can also be used to learn the dynamics of a system from data.

1.6.2 Approximating Function

DNDEs can be used to approximate functions by learning the parameters of a differential equation that best fit a set of data points. This approach can be used to generate high-quality approximations of functions that are difficult to approximate using traditional methods.

1.6.3 Data Compression

DNDEs can be used to compress data by representing it as a set of parameters that can be used to generate the original data. This approach can be used to reduce the size of data sets without losing important information.

1.6.4 Optimal Control

DNDEs can be used to solve optimal control problems by learning the optimal control policy from data. This approach can be used to optimize the behavior of a system in real-time.

1.6.5 Stochastic Processes

DNDEs can be used to model stochastic processes by combining deep neural networks with stochastic differential equations. This approach can be used to predict the behavior of complex systems that are subject to random fluctuations.

2 Preliminaries of Neural Networks

2.1 What is Neural Network?

neural network is a type of machine learning model that is designed to recognize patterns in data. It is loosely modeled after the structure and function of the human brain, and consists of layers of interconnected nodes (neurons) that process information and make decisions based on input data. Neural networks can be used for a variety of tasks, such as image recognition, speech recognition, natural language processing, and prediction. They are especially useful when dealing with complex and high-dimensional data, and can learn from examples to improve their performance over time. There are several types of neural networks, including feedforward neural networks, recurrent neural networks, and convolutional neural networks, each of which is suited to different types of problems.

Figure 1: Neural Network

2.2 Biological Neural Network

A biological neural network refers to the network of interconnected neurons that make up the nervous system of living organisms, including the brain, spinal cord, and peripheral nervous system. These neurons communicate with each other through electrochemical signals, forming complex circuits that allow for information processing, sensory perception, and motor control. Here is an image of a simplified diagram of a biological neural network in

the brain: This image shows a single neuron with dendrites (receiving) inputs from other neurons), a cell body (where the inputs are integrated), an axon (transmitting output signals to other neurons), and synapses (the points of communication between neurons). In the brain, billions of neurons form complex networks that allow for the processing and interpretation of sensory information, motor control, and cognitive functions such as memory, learning, and decision-making. The study of biological neural networks has inspired the development of artificial neural networks, which are used in machine learning and artificial intelligence applications. Neural networks can be used in different fields. The tasks to which artificial neural networks are applied tend to fall within the following broad categories: Function approximation, or regression analysis, including time series prediction and modeling. Classification, including pattern and sequence recognition, novelty detection and sequential decision making. Data processing, including filtering, clustering, blind signal separation and compression. Application areas of ANNs include nonlinear system identification[37] and control (vehicle control, process control), game-playing and decision making (backgammon, chess, racing), pattern recognition (radar systems, face identification, object recognition), sequence recognition (gesture, speech, handwritten text recognition), medical diagnosis, financial applications, data mining (or knowledge discovery in databases, "KDD"), visualization and e-mail spam filtering. For example, it is possible to create a semantic profile of user's interests emerging from pictures trained for object recognition.

Figure 2: Biological Neural Network

2.3 Mathematical model of Artificial Neural Network

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are mathematical models used for processing and classifying data. The basic building block of an ANN is a neuron, which receives inputs from other neurons, processes them, and produces an output. The mathematical model of a neuron is based on the concept of a weighted sum of inputs. The inputs are multiplied by their respective weights, and the products are summed up. The resulting sum is then passed through a non-linear function, known as an activation function, to produce the output of the neuron. This process is mathematically expressed as follows:

$$f(w * x + b)$$

where y is the output of the neuron, x is the input vector, w is the weight vector, b is the bias term, and f is the activation function. The most commonly used activation function is the sigmoid function, which has a characteristic S-shaped curve. Other popular activation functions include the hyperbolic tangent function and the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) function. The mathematical model of an ANN is built by connecting multiple neurons together in layers. The input layer receives the input data, and the output layer produces the final output of the network. The hidden layers, located between the input and output layers, perform the intermediate computations. The connections between neurons are represented by a matrix of weights, which are adjusted during the training phase to optimize the performance of the network. The mathematical model of an ANN can be expressed using matrix multiplication and vector addition, which allows for efficient computation on modern hardware. The forward propagation algorithm, which computes the output of the network given the input, is implemented as a sequence of matrix multiplications and activation functions applied to the intermediate results. The backward propagation algorithm, which adjusts the weights of the network during training, is implemented using the chain rule of calculus to compute the gradients of the loss function with respect to the weights. Overall, the mathematical model of an ANN is a powerful tool for solving complex problems in a wide range of fields, including image and speech recognition, natural language processing, and predictive analytics.

Figure 3: Mathematical model of ANN

2.4 Activation Function

In machine learning, an activation function is a mathematical function applied to the output of a neuron or node in a neural network. It determines whether the neuron should be activated or not based on whether the inputs it receives are relevant for the output it produces. The activation function introduces non-linearity into the network, which enables the neural network to model complex patterns and relationships in the data. Without an activation function, the neural network would be limited to linear transformations, which are less powerful. There are several types of activation functions used in neural networks, including: Sigmoid, linear activation function.

2.4.1 Sigmoid Function

The sigmoid activation function is a mathematical function commonly used in artificial neural networks to introduce non-linearity into the output of a neuron or a layer of neurons. It is a type of logistic function that maps any input value to a value between 0 and 1. The sigmoid function is defined as:

$$f(x) = 1/(1 + e^x)$$

where e is the mathematical constant approximately equal to 2.71828, and x is the input value. The sigmoid function has an S-shaped curve that is continuous and differentiable, which makes it useful for training neural networks using gradient descent optimization algorithms. When the input to the sigmoid function is positive, the output tends towards 1, while for negative

input values, the output approaches 0. The sigmoid function is commonly used as an activation function in the output layer of binary classification tasks, where the goal is to predict a binary output, such as a yes or no answer. It is also used in some hidden layers of neural networks, although its use has been largely replaced by other activation functions, such as ReLU, due to some of its drawbacks, such as the vanishing gradient problem.

Figure 4: sigmoid activation function

2.4.2 Linear Activation Function

In the context of artificial neural networks, the linear activation function refers to a simple mathematical function that maps the input to the output linearly. In other words, the output is proportional to the input, with a constant scaling factor. The most common linear activation function is the identity function $f(x) = x$, which simply returns the input as the output. Other examples of linear activation functions include the softmax function used in multiclass classification tasks, and the rectified linear unit (ReLU) used in deep learning architectures. Linear activation functions are often used in the output layer of regression models, where the goal is to predict a continuous output variable. However, they are not commonly used in the hidden layers of deep neural networks, since they are unable to model nonlinear relationships between the inputs and the outputs.

2.5 Neural Network Architecture

2.5.1 Feed Forward Neural Networks

A feedforward neural network (also known as a multilayer perceptron or MLP) is a type of artificial neural network where information flows only in one direction, from the input layer to the output layer. This makes it a non-recurrent neural network, which means it does not have any feedback loops. In a feed-forward neural network, the input data is first passed through the input layer, which consists of neurons that receive the input signals. These signals are then propagated to the hidden layers, which are composed of several layers of neurons that process the input and extract features. Finally, the output layer produces the final result, which can be a classification or a regression prediction. Each neuron in the network is connected to the neurons in the next layer through a set of weights, which are adjusted during the training phase of the network. The goal of training the network is to find the optimal set of weights that minimize the error between the predicted output and the actual output. Feedforward neural networks are widely used in various fields, such as computer vision, natural language processing, speech recognition, and many others. They are highly adaptable and can be used for a wide range of applications, from simple classification tasks to complex pattern recognition and prediction problems.

2.5.2 Radial Basis Function(RBF) Neural Networks

A Radial Basis Function (RBF) neural network is a type of artificial neural network that is primarily used for function approximation and pattern recognition. It is composed of three layers: an input layer, a hidden layer, and an output layer. The hidden layer consists of radial basis functions, which are used to map the input space to a higher-dimensional feature space. In an RBF network, the radial basis functions are used to compute the activation of the hidden layer neurons. The input to each neuron is the Euclidean distance between the input vector and the center of the corresponding radial basis function. The activation of the neuron is then computed using a Gaussian function, which is centered on the input to the neuron. The output layer of an RBF network typically consists of a single neuron, which computes a weighted sum of the outputs from the hidden layer neurons. The weights in the output layer are typically learned using a supervised learning algorithm such as backpropagation. RBF networks are popular for a variety of ap-

plications, including function approximation, classification, and time series prediction. They are particularly useful for problems that involve non-linear relationships between the input and output variables.

2.5.3 Hopfield Networks

Hopfield networks are a type of artificial neural network that can be used to solve optimization problems, including solving certain types of differential equations. One such type of differential equation that can be solved using Hopfield networks is the boundary value problem (BVP) for second-order ordinary differential equations (ODEs). A BVP involves finding the solution to an ODE subject to certain boundary conditions. To solve a BVP using a Hopfield network, the ODE is first discretized, or approximated, using a numerical method such as finite differences or finite elements. The resulting system of equations is then used to define the energy function of the Hopfield network, which is a measure of the network's ability to satisfy the boundary conditions. The Hopfield network is trained to find the values of the unknown function at the discrete points in the domain that minimize the energy function subject to the boundary conditions. Once trained, the network can be used to efficiently and accurately solve the BVP for any set of boundary conditions within the domain. Hopfield networks can also be used to solve other types of differential equations, such as partial differential equations, by discretizing them and using the resulting system of equations to define the energy function of the network. However, the effectiveness of the method depends on the specific properties of the differential equation and the numerical method used for discretization.

3 Formulation and Implementation of ANN Methods for Solving Differential Equations

3.1 Neural Network as Universal Approximation

Neural networks have been shown to be a powerful tool for approximating functions, and this includes approximating solutions to differential equations. In fact, it has been shown that under certain conditions, neural networks can act as universal approximators for a wide class of differential equations. To understand this, it's important to first understand what a differential

equation is. A differential equation is an equation that relates a function to its derivatives. For example, the equation

$$dy/dx = x^2$$

relates the function $y(x)$ to its derivative dy/dx , which is equal to x^2 . The solution to a differential equation is a function that satisfies the equation. For example, the solution to the above equation is

$$y(x) = (1/3)x^3 + C$$

where C is a constant of integration. When it comes to approximating solutions to differential equations using neural networks, the idea is to use the neural network to approximate the solution function. The neural network takes in the input variable(s) (e.g. x) and outputs an approximation of the solution function. To make this work, the neural network needs to be trained on a set of data that includes both input-output pairs (i.e. values of x and the corresponding values of $y(x)$) as well as derivatives of the solution function (i.e. values of dy/dx for the corresponding values of x). This allows the neural network to learn the underlying relationship between the input variable and the solution function, as well as the relationship between the solution function and its derivatives. Under certain conditions, such as the continuity and boundedness of the solution function and its derivatives, it has been shown that neural networks can approximate the solution to a wide class of differential equations with arbitrary accuracy. This is known as the universal approximation theorem for neural networks. However, it's important to note that in practice, the accuracy of the approximation may depend on factors such as the complexity of the differential equation and the quality of the training data.

3.2 Universal Approximation Theorem

The Universal Approximation Theorem (UAT) for Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs) states that a feedforward neural network with a single hidden layer containing a finite number of neurons can approximate any continuous function on a compact input space to arbitrary accuracy, provided that the activation function used in the hidden layer is non-constant, bounded, and monotonically-increasing. In other words, given any continuous function $f(x)$ defined on a compact input space X , and any desired level of accuracy

$\epsilon > 0$, there exists a feedforward neural network with a single hidden layer containing a finite number of neurons, and with appropriate weights and biases, such that the difference between the output of the network and the true value of the function at any point x in X is less than ϵ .

$$y_k = y_k(x, w) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_2} w_k^3 \phi\left(\sum_{j=0}^n w_k^2 x_j\right), k = 1, 2, \dots, m$$